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THE SIGNIFICANCE, ROLE AND PLACE OF COMPUTER GRAPHICS IN THE INFORMATION SOCIETY

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Abstract. *The composition of information in computer graphics is focused on human senses of sight and hearing. So simple by doing so to speak information to give for image and from sound wide is used. Main the goal information image and to the sound from scrolling consists of.*

Base expressions: *AutoCAD, AutoCAD, ArchiCAD, AutoCAD Electrical, 3ds Max, Design Review, drawing, geometry, drawing geometry, in computer graphics, geometric constructions, for example, dividing a circle into equal parts, passing a circle arc, trigonometry, angle bisectors.*

Introduction. It is known that in the exchange of information, the information received by the human organ of vision is the most effective, and it also leaves a deep impression on the memory. In particular, the information provided by means of sound has a positive effect. The least effective means of information is written information, which takes more time to receive and process in the brain, and due to the physiology of each person, a certain part of the information is lost and stored in memory. [A.1 ;,2;,5] .

Relevance of the topic. The composition of information in computer graphics is focused on human senses of sight and hearing. So simple by doing so to speak information to give for image and from sound wide is used. Main the goal information image and to the sound from scrolling consists of

In scientific research work program studied in the work America’s **Autodesk** firm by work developed **AutoCAD** graphic is a program. **Autodesk** of the firm very many program products there is (AutoCAD, ArchiCAD, AutoCAD Electrical, 3ds Max, Design Review...), whole in the world wide becoming popular gone, eng last technologies in itself embodies. of the firm program products inside **AutoCAD** program important place holds _ It is the main one being and remaining programs his based on

created is considered **AutoCAD** (project automation system), from simple details to large-scale construction projects of any complexity with high precision. Therefore, we can consider this topic as relevant. [A.1 ;,2;] .

Purpose and tasks of work. In this work, the main goal and task is to clarify the capabilities of the AutoCAD program and to create practical problems related to specific sciences (drawing, geometry, drawing geometries) and engineering works using the AutoCAD program, to provide detailed theoretical and practical information about these problems. .

Scientific innovations in work and achieved results. Today, there are many computer graphics programs that differ from each other depending on the field of application. Har one field specialists own activities for comfortable has been graph program they choose Programs chance limits are also known one to the field directed will be So, the graph program in choosing first of all there is his opportunities in consideration get it is necessary The majority cases graph program from applying before another one programs or sciences to master need it is felt. That's it also graph with programs complicated goes _

The graphics capabilities are very high and can handle both simple and complex tasks at the same time. That's it attention it's worth it directly sure sciences closely related to depends. Theirs organic continuation also accepted as to be done possible and of students upcoming the work also useful in activities place holds.

The practical significance of work . As AutoCAD graphics software is concerned with drawing, practical information on simple geometric constructions such as bisecting a circle, arcs, diagonals, diagonals, angle bisectors, and properties of perpendicularity and parallelism and instructions are cited in the thesis [A.1 ;,2;,4] .

The structure of scientific research work. This work consists of an introduction, two chapters, a conclusion and a list of references.real world objects was created in engineering graphics . Then a remote camera is added, which allows changing the point of view of light sources on the object, and finally, the speed of computers has increased, which allows us to see real objects of complex shapes on the screen in full color and in a reasonable time frame, and allows you to know. Thus, he firmly entered the construction and design of graphics. Nowadays, virtually everything, from the latest model of a Ford car to perfume bottles, is designed on computers.

Literature analysis. Prof. published on the implementation and protection of scientific research. I used the methodological instruction of H.QQ arshiboev. During the implementation of this scientific research work, a number of literatures, normative documents , published scientific articles on the topic and materials of internet sites and educational portals were studied, the used and studied literatures were analyzed, and the scientific research work was prepared. . They are reflected in the list of literature

given at the end of the graduation thesis. Among these literatures, I made a complete analysis using the Internet of the materials in the methodical instructions for passing practical training in "Computer graphics" by DFKuchkarova, XAPulatova, BUKhaitov . [A.1 ;,2;,3;,4;,5] .

Summary

Summing up from this work, it is worth emphasizing to users that the following areas of computer graphics application can be broadly divided. Draw graphs — i.e. to display two- and three-dimensional graphs of mathematical, physical or binary relations on the screen or hard copy. Cartography gives a clear idea of geographical, natural or economic phenomena related to countries, regions, regions. Automation of drafting and design work — this is the creation of accurate drawings, details, parts and assemblies, interactive work with the model of the components and systems being designed to check their properties, for example, mechanical, electrical or thermal properties. Modeling and multiplication — *this* is the presentation of real and modeled objects by means of real-time video transformations, interactive cartooning, game programs, etc. Process management — is to work with real-world perspectives in an interactive way and present the quantities coming from sensors installed at important points of the system. Art and advertising — is to reflect the intended meaning and attract the attention of the audience with the help of aesthetically pleasing images. Another area of application of the computer graphics tool is multimedia. The emergence of such systems will, without a doubt, make fundamental changes in such fields as education, science, art, economy. [A.3;,4;,5]

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